

A Simulation Study of Mixed Trucks and Robots for Last Mile Delivery

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Abstract

This paper introduces an approach to enhance the efficiency of last-mile delivery through trucks and robot transport. The primary objective is to alleviate traffic congestion by repurposing pedestrian sidewalks for robot transportation through autonomous vehicles, consequently optimizing the activities of trucks by eliminating the necessity for them to navigate through the city. In addressing this challenge, we formulate an optimization problem and apply it in a case study conducted in the city of Bari, Italy. The city is partitioned into distinct zones, served by a hub, where trucks arrive to unload goods to be delivered to final destinations. The issue is formulated as an optimization problem aimed at maximizing the daily number of deliveries. To assess the proposed solutions under more realistic conditions, we employ modelling and simulation techniques utilizing the Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) software. These simulations consider the influence of road traffic, which has the potential to affect the overall efficiency of the delivery system. The analysis conducted revealed significant advantages of this innovative approach compared to the classical delivery system.

Keywords: Last Mile Logistics, Simulation, Robots

1. Introduction

The processes of goods transportation and distribution are among the main causes of energy consumption, emissions of harmful gases, and noise pollution in urban areas, negatively impacting the quality of life and the environment in cities. In particular, with the proliferation of e-commerce, the movement of goods in urban and metropolitan areas has undergone significant changes in distribution methods. The effect of these trends intensified significantly during the pandemic period (COVID-19), leading to increased traffic and creating further issues for urban mobility.

In such a context, the last mile delivery is considered the most vulnerable link in the supply chain, contributing substantially to urban congestion and environmental pollution, as widely studied by Rodrigue et al. (2009). Specifically, the delivery sector is undergoing numerous changes to fulfil growing consumer demands. Advances in automation technology present the potential to more contemporary, sustainable, and efficient delivery systems, paving the way for innovative delivery models that could reshape the last-mile delivery environment.

The benefits of autonomous transport in urban areas are clear and yield significant advantages, including reduced traffic, mitigation of pollutants, and the ability to operate in areas where limitations are often imposed by municipalities, particularly in historic city centres. Numerous works in the literature introduce various innovative concepts for the transportation and distribution of the goods. An example is a comprehensive review and analysis of the latest trends in last-mile delivery solutions from both industry and academic perspectives conducted by Mohammad et al. (2023).

In freight transport, last-mile distribution of goods has been explored through different aspects such as electric vehicles, drones, trunk deliveries in parked cars, and last-mile deliveries utilizing autonomous robots integrated with trucks.

Moreover, the routing problem is one of the most frequently addressed issues in last mile delivery. It can be modelled and solved explicitly or approximated, using closed form such as continuous approximation equations. This approach provided asymptotic solutions for the shortest path through randomly distributed points (Beardwood et al., 1959), provided valuable insights into cost-effective relationships in large-scale urban freight distribution to optimize transport networks and reduced overall environmental impact (Franceschetti et al., 2017), and enabled the use of a more holistic approach to urban logistics management by integrating real-world constraints (Figliozzi, 2007).

In the research conducted by Alfandari et al. (2022), the problem of minimizing a tardiness indicator based on customer delivery deadlines is addressed by finding an optimal route for a vehicle carrying customer parcels from a central depot to selected facilities, from where autonomous devices like robots are launched to perform last-mile deliveries.

To reduce the overall route duration, Shih-Hao Lu et al. (2022) suggest a model known as the Flexible Drone Traveling Salesman Problem (FDTSP) aimed at minimizing the total delivery time. In this model, the truck serves as a mobile launch platform for the drones, delivering packages to customers and substituting for drone delivery when needed, while the drones efficiently distribute packages to maximize customer coverage.

The use of autonomous delivery robots is addressed to deliver small goods by the authors Poeting et al. (2019), Bakach et al. (2021) and Srinivas et al. (2022). In the more congested areas of the city, the authors Boysen et al. (2018), Ostermeier et al. (2022) and Simoni et al. (2020) have demonstrated the effectiveness of employing the truck-robot system, especially when the robot can transport multiple parcels.

Indeed, Heimfarth et al. (2022) propose the first mixed truck and robot delivery concept with robot depots in which both robots and the delivery truck can visit customers.

Their tailored solution approach is based on a General Variable Neighbourhood Search that efficiently solves the routing problem and outperforms existing truck-and-robot routing algorithms.

Interesting literature fields that have emerged in the research concern simulation models for evaluating urban logistics vehicles and mixed fleet studies. In the first stream, dynamic simulations using a new robotized vehicle designed for urban freight transport demonstrated the reduction of delivery times and improved efficiency in congested urban areas (Silvestri et al., 2019). Additionally sustainable alternatives to cut traffic congestion and emissions, especially in densely populated urban areas, include the use of cargo cycles, integrated into urban logistics (Melo and Baptista, 2017), the use of collaborative multi-drone truck system (Thomas et al., 2023), and combination of drones and trucks (Rave et al., 2023), which also reduces total delivery times and operational costs.

In this scenario, simulation and optimization assume crucial roles, with the former serving as a decision support tool and the latter finding widespread application in various works that focus on urban distribution. A Discrete Event Simulation (DES) model that evaluates the vehicle routes in terms of their impact on the expected total costs in a location routing problem is analysed in (Herazo-Padilla et al. 2015).

In the context of the last mile delivery, the effects of different delivery approaches have been quantified with the support of simulation by Arnold et al. (2018). The authors carefully modelled the delivery processes and utilized a set of real-world datasets and realistic cost values. Based on these inputs, they simulated and analysed the current state-of-the-practice in the distribution of e-commerce goods in an urban area and compared it to possible 'what-if' scenarios. Alvarez-Palau et al. (2022) employ real-life data gathered from the largest food delivery platforms (Just Eat, Glovo, and Deliveroo) operating in the city of Barcelona (Spain) to analyse the profitability of these business models. The authors develop a Monte Carlo simulation model with several scenarios to estimate how many orders are needed to reach economic profitability.

Samouh et al. (2020) propose the combination of different last mile food delivery systems (robot delivery system, drone delivery system and a hybrid delivery system) to analyse the performances of the system with the support of an agent-based simulation in MATLAB. Their conclusions indicate that the hybrid delivery approach is the optimal solution for reducing delivery times. Markus et al. (2020) describe how last-mile deliveries can be considered in a supply chain simulation using distance metrics and names a rescaling factor that can be applied independently of the cityscape. Indeed, in the research conducted by Boussier et al. (2011), a new strategy is implemented using simulation for the sharing of parking spaces between light cars and vans for goods delivery.

Perboli et al. (2018) use the multimodal transportation to reduce emissions in the environment. At the same time, the authors do not set themselves the goal of reducing the delivery time. Furthermore, a simulation based on the Monte Carlo method and optimization modules are defined directly in Python and the realism of case study is guaranteed by the introduction in the framework of different real data sources and stakeholder requirements. The research results highlighted that the switch to vehicles with a low environmental impact and to lockers, could lead an improvement in the economic efficiency of the business model of the traditional carrier and in the working conditions of the drivers. Another similar problem is considered by Simoni et al. (2020) that exploits a very efficient and special dynamic programming solution in the "Weighted Interval Scheduling Problem". Moreover, Boysen et al. (2018) introduce a proficient heuristic solution method aimed at minimizing the weighted count of delayed customer deliveries. This involves a scheduling procedure that delineates the truck route, considering both

robot depots and drop-off points. Even if different solutions are proposed for the last mile delivery problem, few works try to apply the proposed approaches to real case studies.

The aim of this paper is to propose and test a last mile delivery strategy that compares traditional delivery with trucks and delivery by autonomous vehicles (robots) that depart from hubs where the trucks have unloaded the goods. This last innovative approach was developed starting from the ideas proposed in recent scientific literature (Boysen et al., 2018, Heimfarth et al. 2022 and Krendeleva et al. 2023). The urban area is divided into a set of zones and each zone is managed by a hub where the trucks arrive to deliver the goods into the zone. In the hub the parcels are unloaded from the truck and loaded into the robot. Once the loading activity is complete, the robot heads towards the customer. In this study, we focus on a single area, the historic city centre, which is marked by several constraints. The characteristic of this area is that it is pedestrian, consequently vehicles cannot have direct access but must stop in parking lots. These parking lots are outside and near the historic city centre, and the delivery of goods must be on foot. In addition, these parking lots are located on the peri-urban street that runs along the entire old core of the city. The study is configured within the problem of peri-urban roads.

In particular, the last-mile delivery with robots is analysed by a methodology composed of three main phases. First, the process is described by the Unified Modelling Language (UML) activity diagram (Miles and Hamilton, 2006) to single out the main activities and actors of the process. Then, an optimization problem is carried out that maximizes the number of deliveries per day, based on estimated delivery times, considering different parcel sizes and robot loading capacities. The proposed method allows providing results with fast processing time, related to a cluster of customers in each zone rather than of exact assignment for each customer with much more longer processing time. Finally, we test the proposed procedures by Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) software to evaluate the solutions in a more realistic environment that also includes traffic of bicycles and pedestrians. In addition, the proposed approach is compared with a standard delivery process where trucks drivers park in different lots and then deliver the parcels.

To evaluate the effectiveness of this methodology, we apply it to a case study involving the historic city centre of Bari (a city of Southern Italy). The solution is studied and simulated across various robot speeds and compared with deliveries conducted by truck and human couriers. The results point out the benefits of the new strategy.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem description. Section 3 describes the proposed methodology; while Section 4 examines the two case studies and proposes the optimal solution for each case. Section 5 describes the simulation model and presents the simulation results. Section 6 discusses the results obtained. Finally, Section 7 provides conclusions and future research.

2. Problem Description

This section describes the two last mile delivery approaches analysed in this paper. First, a standard delivery approach is presented where trucks use the parking lots distributed at different sites in the city and human operators perform the deliveries (delivery Process A). Second, in a modern approach, trucks arrive in suitable hubs, where parcels are loaded onto the robots, that execute the deliveries (delivery Process B). In the following the two delivery processes are described in detail.

The objective of the problem is to maximize the number of parcels that each of the two logistics strategies can deliver. Such object is justified by the assumption that the couriers and the robots have a constant speed and a specific working time to perform the deliveries. Hence, the goal is maximizing the number of parcels by also providing the

necessary number of robots to be used. This aspect is an additional advantage of the proposed approach with respect to the adoption of human workers.

In this study, different parcel sizes and weights are considered. The parcels are classified into three sizes: small, medium and large. We assume the parcel weight follows the same classification of the parcel sizes, considering linearly growth of parcels (e.g., a small parcel is light, a medium parcel is medium, and a large parcel is heavy).

Figure 1 describes the delivery Process A under standard conditions. The truck driver, after loading the truck in the warehouse, heads towards the first delivery zone where there are the first customers. Process A begins when the truck makes its first parking in the city: activities take place with the vehicle being parked in an area near to the customer to facilitate delivery on-foot (Activity 1). The truck operator delivers one or two parcels at a time, considering the parcels sizes. In case of small parcels, it is possible to carry two parcels at a time, otherwise only one parcel. If there are multiple parcels to deliver nearby, the driver returns to the parking area and retrieves another parcel or two from the truck for delivery (Activity 2). Only when the truck driver has delivered all the parcels in the area, he/she returns to the truck and heads towards a new parking lot to deliver other parcels (Activity 3).

Figure 1. Standard delivery Process A

Figure 2 describes Process B. In this case, the urban area is divided into a set of zones and each zone is managed by a hub where the trucks arrive to deliver the goods in the zone. Process B starts when the truck arrives to the hub: the first activity is the unloading of the parcels at the hub. Within the hub there is a fleet of autonomous vehicles (robots) ready to deliver parcels within the competence zone (Activity 1). An operator of the hub loads the parcels into the robot (Activity 2), considering the parcels sizes. In case of small parcels, it is possible to carry three parcels at a time; in case of medium parcels, it is possible to carry two parcels at a time, otherwise only one parcel. Once the loading activity task is completed, the robot heads towards the customer (Activity 3). Upon completing the delivery, the robot returns to its zone hub (Activity 4), and once recharged, it is ready for a new delivery. Each hub is the initial and destination of each robot and is reachable via designated routes accessible to pedestrians, bicycles, or micro-electric vehicles.

Figure 2. Robot delivery Process B

It is pointed out that the problem focuses on the final stage of parcel delivery within the city, exactly the last mile delivery. Therefore, the activity in which the truck leaves the warehouse and arrives in the city (at the first parking area, for process A, or at the hub, for process B) is common to both processes and then is not considered in the problem formulation. The main objective is to compare and evaluate the performance of the two processes, and in this case, the results of this activity (transportation the parcels by truck from the warehouse into the city) would be the same in each process.

Moreover, Table 1 and Table 2 respectively list the activities mentioned in each delivery process.

Table 1. Description of the activities to be performed in Process A”.

N°	Activity	Description
1	Parking Area	Once the truck driver reaches the parking near the customer, the parcel is unloaded
2	Customer delivery	The truck driver reaches the customer and delivers the parcel
3	Truck driver return	Truck driver returns to parking Area

Table 2. Description of the activities to be performed in delivery Process B

N°	Activity	Description
1	Hub zone	Once the truck driver reaches the hub, the parcels are unloaded
2	Parcel Upload	The hub operator verifies order and loads parcel into robot
3	Customer delivery	The robot reaches the customer and delivers the parcel
4	Robot return	Robot returns to hub

In the following sections, the methodology developed for optimizing and evaluating the performance of Process A and B I described. The methodology is composed of three main steps.

In Step 1 a UML activity diagram is used to describe in a standardized way the process activities and the corresponding actors.

In Step 2, the problem is formulated as an optimization problem that maximizes the number of deliveries per day (in a given time period), considering sizes of parcels, based on the evaluated delivery times.

In Step 3, last-mile delivery process with driver-truck is simulated by Google Maps (Process A), while the use of robots is simulated by SUMO (Process B) to test the proposed procedures and solutions in a realistic environment including bicycles and pedestrian traffic. This step requires the specification of a case study as it uses maps and data specific to a certain geographical area. Therefore, step 3 is described in a dedicated Section.

3. Description of the last-mile delivery process A

3.1 UML description of last-mile delivery - process A

This sub-section describes in detail tasks performed by truck-driver through a UML approach. A UML activity diagram (Miles and Hamilton, 2006) is used to describe in a standardized way the process activities and the corresponding actors. The UML activity diagrams are powerful tools suitable to describe in detail the complexity of the system behavior. Indeed, they allow for the representation of parallel elaborations to explain the critical points in the processes by pointing out all the possible paths, parallel activities and their subdivisions. The main elements of these diagrams are: the initial activity (denoted by a solid circle); the final activity (denoted by a bull's eye symbol); other activities, represented by a rectangle with rounded edges; arcs, representing flows, connecting activities; forks and joins, depicted by a horizontal split, used for representing concurrent activities and actions respectively beginning and ending at the same time; decisions, representing alternative flows and depicted by a diamond, with options written on either sides of the arrows emerging from the diamond; signals representing activities sending or receiving a message, which can be of two types: input signals (message receiving activities), shown by a concave polygon, and output signals (message sending activities), shown by a convex polygon. Moreover, partitions or swim lanes are used to show which actor is responsible for which actions.

Figure 3 specifies the actors involved in the standard delivery process and the corresponding operations:

- **Truck driver:** he /she organizes the parcels according to their destination or intended delivery sequence, ensuring on-time delivery. Locates the delivery zone and once reached finds the nearest parking area. Handles delivery to customer's house by walking short distances.
- **Customer:** he /she follows simple procedures that help ensure efficient delivery, checking only that the package matches the order (company of origin, recipient, due date).

Figure 3. UML diagram for the standard delivery Process A

The traditional last-mile delivery, performed by truck-driver in pedestrian areas such as historic city centre, is characterized by: i) assessment of customers in the area, ii) clustering of customers in each sub-zones, iii) assignment of sub-zones to existing parking lots, iv) assessment of the parcels size to be delivered (possibility of carrying two small at a time, and one medium or large at a time), v) calculation of time required based on time available, vi) finalization of tasks.

3.2 The optimization model of last-mile delivery - process A

In this section the optimization model for process A is described. The objective function to be maximized is the number of parcels delivered per day in the given period T .

The optimization model is formulated under the following assumptions:

- the city is divided into a set of zones, based on the number of citizens and the morphological conformation of the city;
- parking areas are identified for each zone to be used for delivery on foot;
- sub-zones are created in each zone based on the distance to the parking areas;
- in each zone, each customer is placed in one sub-zone;
- parcels vary in size and weight and are classified into small, medium and large;
- truck-driver can deliver two small parcels or one medium or large parcel per trip
- customers are clustered by proximity in the same sub-zone so that multiple deliveries (one or two parcels) can be made quickly in the same sub-zone;
- multiple deliveries do not consider individual customer distances but an incremental time is added in the case of two parcels;
- deliveries performed in the sub-zone assigned to a parking area, start from and return to the truck.

Based on these assumptions, the delivery time of double delivery is increased of the 20% of a single delivery.

The data of the problem are described in the following:

- each zone is partitioned in a set $A = \{a_i \mid i = 1, \dots, I\}$ of $I \in \mathbb{N}_0$ sub-zones, where \mathbb{N}_0 stands for the set of integer positive numbers included the zero.
- $Z = \{j=1, \dots, J\}$ set of the parking areas.
- $\tau_{A,i}^s$ is the delivery time of the truck driver to perform one delivery in the sub-zone $a_i \in A$, in case of single parcel;
- $\tau_{A,i}^t$ is the delivery time of the truck driver to perform one delivery in the sub-zone $a_i \in A$, in case of two parcels;
- t_{APzj} is the time to move from the parking area $z \in Z$ to parking area $j \in Z$ and park the truck.

The decision variables are the following:

- $n_{A,i}^s$ is the number of single parcels delivered in the sub-zone $a_i \in A$;
- $n_{A,i}^t$ is the number of double parcels delivered in the sub-zone $a_i \in A$.

Moreover, we denote by T_A the time that in one day is spent to deliver single and double parcels in all the sub-zones and to move the truck from one parking area to another.

$$T_A = \sum_{i=1}^I (\tau_{A,i}^s \cdot n_{A,i}^s + \tau_{A,i}^t \cdot n_{A,i}^t) + \sum_{z=1}^J \sum_{j=1, z < j}^J t_{APzj}$$

The optimization problem is defined as follows:

$$\text{Max} \sum_{i=1}^I (n_{A,i}^s + n_{A,i}^t) \quad (1)$$

s.t.:

$$\sum_{i=1}^I (\tau_{A,i}^s \cdot n_{A,i}^s + \tau_{A,i}^t \cdot n_{A,i}^t) + \sum_{z=1}^J \sum_{j=1}^J t_{APzj} \leq T \quad (2)$$

$$(n_{A,i}^s + n_{A,i}^t) \geq 1 \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, I. \quad (3)$$

Constraint (2) is introduced to guarantee that all the deliveries are performed in the maximum time T . Constraints (3) impose that at least one parcel is delivered per sub-zone.

4. Description of the last-mile delivery process B

This section describes the innovative approach for the last mile delivery, developed specifically for the pedestrian areas. These areas are characterized by several mobility constraints, such as no truck access, reduced air and noise emissions, which significantly affect traditional approaches to urban logistics.

4.1 UML description of Delivery Process B

In Fig. 4, actors and their corresponding activities related to the robot delivery process are described:

- **Truck:** it arrives to the hub and parcels are unloaded. The truck driver is not involved in the process B. After arriving at the hub and unloading parcels, the driver returns to the warehouse or leaves for a new task without having to do anything for this process.
- **Hub Operator:** he /she organizes parcels based on their destination or the planned delivery sequence. This ensures that the robot can carry out deliveries efficiently, following delivery orders. Additionally, he/she ensures the stable and secure

placement of parcels inside the autonomous delivery vehicle. When necessary, the operator takes care of battery charging or sensor cleaning.

- **Robot:** it receives the parcel from the hub operator, autonomously navigates towards the customer, completes a parcel delivery, and returns to the hub. If there is enough time, it starts again for a new delivery.
- **Customer:** the customer unloads the parcel and verifies that the parcel is in accordance with the order (e.g., the company, the material, the recipient).

In Process B, each zone is associated with a hub. The peculiarity is that the final destinations in each hub can be reached by pedestrians, bicycles, light electric vehicles, and robots through reserved routes, thereby freeing up traffic on the roads.

Figure 4. UML diagram for the robot delivery Process B

4.2 The Optimization Model

To maximize the number of deliveries per day (in a given period T), an optimization model is formulated under the following assumptions:

- delivery processes involve dividing the city into a set of zones, based on the number of citizens and the morphological conformation of the city;
- each zone is assigned a hub where there is a fleet of robots;
- sub-zones are created in each zone based on the distance to the hub;
- in each zone, each customer is placed in one sub-zone;
- parcels vary in size and weight and are classified into small, medium and large;
- robots have a capacity that depends on the type of parcels, which allows for multiple deliveries within the area;
- during the considered period T , robots do not need to be charged because they have sufficient autonomy to complete all delivery tasks;
- customers are clustered by proximity in the same sub-zone so that multiple deliveries (one, two or three parcels) can be performed in the same sub-zone;

- multiple deliveries are completed by adding an incremental time of 20% and 40% of a single delivery in the case of two parcels and three parcels, respectively. This is a simplifying assumption that estimates an average value of the additional time for moving within the same sub-area (without returning to the hub) to deliver one or two additional parcels;
- each robot has to deliver N parcels to a set of customers belonging to the zone, starting from and returning to the hub.

The variables and data of the problem are described in the following:

- each zone is partitioned in a set $A = \{a_i \mid i = 1, \dots, I\}$ of $I \in \mathbb{N}_0$ sub-zones;
- $K_D = \{k \mid k = 1, \dots, K\}$ is the set of type of deliveries, where k denotes the number of parcels delivered by a robot;
- $R_D = \{r \mid r = 1, \dots, R\}$ is the set of robots;
- $N_{i,k} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is the maximum number of parcels of type $k \in K$ that all robots can deliver in sub-zone $a_i \in A$. It is calculated by a mathematical formula that considers the capacity of robots and the different combination of parcels that can be carried on a single robot (considering a trip with one small, or two small, or three small, or one small and one medium, or one medium, or two medium, or one large);
- $\tau_{Bi}^r \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the delivery time for robot $r \in R$ to perform one delivery in the sub-zone $a_i \in A$;
- N is the total number of parcels to be delivered in time T .

Each subzone $a_i \in A$ is characterized by the distance d_i from the parking area/hub to the customer and the time τ_{Bi}^r necessary for delivering into the sub-zone $a_i \in A$ the parcels (the time to reach the customers, unload the parcels, and return to the parking area/hub). The requested number of deliveries for each subzone is of N parcels.

The decision variables are the following:

- $D_{i,k,r} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is the number of parcels delivered in sub-zone $a_i \in A$, of type $k \in K_D$ by robot $r \in R_D$.
- T_{max} is the time of the last delivery performed by the robots.

The objective function maximizes the number of parcels to be delivered in the minimum time $T_{max} \leq T$.

The optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\text{Max} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{r=1}^R [k \cdot D_{i,k,r}] - \alpha T_{max} \quad (4)$$

s.t.:

$$\sum_{r=1}^R D_{i,k,r} \leq N_{i,k} \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, I \text{ and } k = 1, \dots, K \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{r=1}^R D_{i,k,r} \geq 1 \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, I \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K [(0,2 \cdot k + 0,8) \cdot D_{i,k,r} \cdot \tau_{Bi}^r] \leq T_{max} \quad \text{for } r = 1, \dots, R \quad (7)$$

$$T_{max} \leq T. \quad (8)$$

Constraints (5) are introduced to consider the capacity of robots based on the different types of parcels delivered (small, medium, and large). Constraints (6) require at least one parcel to be delivered per sub-zone. Constraints (7) imposes that the working time of each robot to deliver the parcels is minor or equal to the available maximum time. In the formula (7) the weight $(0.2 \cdot k + 0.8)$ takes into account the size of the parcels that increases of 0.2 for each type of parcel k . Constraint (8) imposes that the time of the last delivery is less or equal to T . Moreover, α is a weight of small value to prioritize the number of deliveries.

The problem always admits a feasible solution because the number of parcels delivered may be less than the customer demand based on a given period: with less time available, the number of parcels delivered will decrease.

5. Case Study

In this section, we solve and simulate a case study involving the city of Bari, located in southern Italy. The city centre is divided into four zones, as shown in Fig. 5:

1. “Bari old town” named Zone_A,
2. “Murat zone” named Zone_B,
3. “Umbertino zone” named Zone_C,
4. “Madonnella zone” named Zone_D.

The case study analyzes only Zone_A, the pedestrian area of the historic city centre.

Figure 5. The city of Bari and the delivery zones

In addition, Zone_A is divided in $I=10$ subzones based on the distance between the parking lots outside the historic city centre, located along the peri-urban road, and the customers within the area. The parcels are of three categories: small parcels (SP), medium parcels (MP) and large parcels (LP). Table 3 presents the parcel demand in a working day for subzone and category: 48 small parcels, 35 medium parcels and 17 large parcels.

Table 3. Parcel demand in a working day by subzones of Zone A

a_i	SP	MP	LP
a_1	6	4	1
a_2	4	2	2
a_3	5	4	1
a_4	6	5	2
a_5	4	3	2
a_6	4	4	2
a_7	3	2	2
a_8	4	5	2
a_9	6	3	1
a_{10}	6	3	2
N	48	35	17

5.1 Case Study: last-mile delivery - process A

In delivery Process A, we assume that each zone is served by a single truck driver (courier) that delivers the parcels. The truck driver reaches a sub-zone closest to their customer, looks for a parking area and then walks to the customer. After the delivery, the courier returns to the truck and heads to another sub-zone to make a new delivery. A courier performs the deliveries with an average walking speed of $v_c=5$ km/h in all the subzones. In Process A, the truck driver must search for the nearest parking area for each sub-zone and performs the delivery by walking. We assume that the average walking truck driver speed is equal in each subzone.

The maximum number of deliveries per day for zone A is $N=100$ (the parcel demand shown in Table 3) and the courier involved in this delivery process works 8 hours per day, with 20 minutes break every 2 hours corresponding to 60 minutes per work shift. This corresponds to a total daily working time of $T=420$ minutes. Parking areas along the peri-urban roads in the historic city centre are limited. In this case study, three parking areas are assumed to be used by the truck driver to meet the delivery needs.

The delivery times of the truck driver ($\tau_{A,i}^s$ and $\tau_{A,i}^t$) are obtained in process A to perform one delivery in the i -th sub-zone. It is calculated as the sum of the following process times:

- *Average time to unload the parcel from the truck;*
- *Average delivery time from parking area to customer and return (t_{A_i}):* the time required to transport a parcel from the parking area to the final customer and go back in each i -th sub-zone;
- *Average waiting time at the customer's location for parcel pickup:* the average waiting time spent by the truck driver waiting to deliver the parcel to the customer.

In addition, in the optimization we assume constant the time t_{APzj} to move from parking area $z \in Z$ to parking area $j \in Z$ and park the truck. Tables 4 and 5 contain data for the delivery Process A.

Table 4. Input activities data for delivery Process A

Description		Value	Unit
t_{APzj}		4	[min]
Delivery time of the truck driver $\tau_{A,i}^s$ and $\tau_{A,i}^t$	Average time to unload the parcel from the truck	1	[min]
	Average delivery time from parking area to customer and return	t_{Ai}	[min]
	Average waiting time at the customer's location for parcel pickup	2	[min]

The average delivery times from parking area to customer and return (t_{Ai}) are reported in Table 5. It is calculated by the ratio of the distance d_i and the average walking courier speed v_c . In addition, each sub-zones a_i is allocated in a different parking area $j \in Z$.

Table 5. Average delivery time from parking area to customer and return for Process A

Parking areas	a_i	d_i (m)	t_{Ai} (min)
1	a_1	100	2.39
	a_2	200	4.79
	a_3	300	7.19
	a_4	400	9.59
2	a_5	100	2.39
	a_6	200	4.79
	a_7	300	7.19
	a_8	400	9.59
3	a_9	100	2.39
	a_{10}	200	4.79

Moreover, Table 6 reports for each subzone a_i , the delivery time of the truck driver in process A in case of a single parcel ($\tau_{A,i}^s$) or in case of two parcels ($\tau_{A,i}^t$). Therefore, the total delivery time of the truck driver for process A (T_A) is the total time the courier uses to deliver small, medium and large parcels in a working day.

Table 6. The delivery time of the courier $\tau_{A,i}^s$ and $\tau_{A,i}^t$ obtained in process A

Parking areas	a_i	d_i (m)	$\tau_{A,i}^s$	$\tau_{A,i}^t$
1	a_1	100	5.39	5.87
	a_2	200	7.79	8.75
	a_3	300	10.19	11.73
	a_4	400	12.59	14.51
2	a_5	100	5.39	5.87
	a_6	200	7.79	8.75
	a_7	300	10.19	11.73
	a_8	400	12.59	14.51
3	a_9	100	5.39	5.87
	a_{10}	200	7.79	8.75

In this case study we do not consider the routing of truck since the road to move from one parking lot to another is a fixed route around the historic city centre. The truck driver starts by parking the vehicle in the first parking lot, and after completing the

deliveries of the sub-zones assigned to that parking lot, proceeds to the next parking lot by driving along the peri-urban road to the historic city centre. This fixed route allows the truck to circumnavigate the historic city centre and has no different routing alternatives except with longer routes.

The optimal solution for delivery Process A is obtained by solving problem (1)-(3) and the results are shown in Table 7. The first column reports the considered subzone a_i , the next columns report the number of small, medium and large parcels delivered. It is apparent that only 67 parcels are delivered in the available working day.

Table 7. Number of parcels delivered by the truck driver in a working day.

a_i	SP	MP	LP
a_1	6	4	1
a_2	4	2	2
a_3	4	2	1
a_4	6	0	0
a_5	4	3	2
a_6	4	4	0
a_7	2	0	0
a_8	4	0	0
a_9	6	3	1
a_{10}	6	3	0
N_{max}	74		
T_A	417.67		

5.2 Case Study: last-mile delivery - process B

In Process B, the maximum number of requested deliveries per day is the same as in Process A, so $N=100$ (the parcel demand shown in Table 3). We consider the case where three robots ($R=3$) are involved in the last-mile delivery process with $T=480$ minutes, comparable to the time of a working day of a truck driver. We assume that the robots have an autonomy, which allows them to do deliveries without recharging. In the considered scenario, Robot 1 and Robot 2 move at an average speed of 6 km/h for distances ranging from 0 to 500m and at an average speed of 8 km/h for distances from 500 m to 1000 m. Robot 3 moves at an average speed of 16 km/h across all distances from 0 to 1000 m.

The *delivery time for each r -th robot t_{Bi}^r* (min) is obtained in Process B to perform one delivery in the i -th sub-zone. It is calculated as the sum of the following process times:

- *average loading time for each robot = 2 min*: time required to load a robot;
- *average unloading time for each customer = 3 min*: time required to unload the parcel from a robot to the end customer;
- *delivery time from hub to customer and return t_{Bi}^r* (min): it is the time required by robot $r \in R$ to transport a parcel from the hub to the final customer and go back in a sub-zone $a_i \in A$. In particular, t_{Bi}^r is obtained by the ratio of distance d_i and the value of the robot speed (Table 8).

The delivery time of each robot τ_{Bi}^r is obtained by considering subzone a_i and the distance of the subzone d_i from the hub (Table 9).

Table 8. Delivery time of robots from hub to customer and return for Process B

a_i	d_i (m)	Robot 1	Robot 2	Robot 3
		t_{Bi}^1 (min)	t_{Bi}^2 (min)	t_{Bi}^3 (min)
a_1	100	1.00	1.00	0.38
a_2	200	2.00	2.00	0.75
a_3	300	3.00	3.00	1.13
a_4	400	4.00	4.00	1.50
a_5	500	5.00	5.00	1.88
a_6	600	4.5	4.5	2.25
a_7	700	5.26	5.26	2.63
a_8	800	6.02	6.02	3.01
a_9	900	6.77	6.77	3.34
a_{10}	1000	7.52	7.52	3.76

Table 9. Delivery time for each robot τ_{Bi}^r in Process B.

a_i	d_i (m)	Robot 1	Robot 2	Robot 3
		τ_{Bi}^1 (min)	τ_{Bi}^2 (min)	τ_{Bi}^3 (min)
a_1	100	7.00	7.00	5.76
a_2	200	9.00	9.00	6.50
a_3	300	11.00	11.00	7.26
a_4	400	13.00	13.00	8.00
a_5	500	15.00	15.00	8.76
a_6	600	14.00	14.00	9.50
a_7	700	15.52	15.52	10.26
a_8	800	17.04	17.04	11.02
a_9	900	18.54	18.54	11.68
a_{10}	1000	20.04	20.04	12.52

5.3 Optimal solutions of the delivery Process B

The formulated ILP problem (4) – (8) is solved by a standard solver, i.e., Excel program on Intel-Core i7, 3,4 Ghz CPU with 8 GB RAM. Table 10 shows the number of small, medium, and large parcels delivered by each robot in the sub-zones and the time $T_{max}=337.89$ minutes necessary to perform all the deliveries, considering the time period of $T=480$ minutes.

To evaluate how the number of deliveries can decrease if the considered time period decreases, we perform the optimization by using $T= 300$ minutes. Table 11 shows that in such a case only 95 parcels are delivered.

Table 10. Process B: Number of parcels delivered by the robots with $T=480$ minutes

a_i	Robot 1			Robot 2			Robot 3		
	SP	MP	LP	SP	MP	LP	SP	MP	LP
a_1	0	2	0	6	2	1	0	0	0
a_2	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	2	2
a_3	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	6	1
a_4	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	4	3
a_5	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	4
a_6	3	4	0	0	0	3	0	0	0
a_7	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	2
a_8	0	0	2	0	2	1	3	2	1
a_9	0	2	2	6	0	0	0	0	0
a_{10}	0	2	3	6	0	0	0	0	0
N_{max}	20			31			49		
T_{max}	337.06			337.89			336.73		

Table 11. Process B: Number of parcels delivered by the robots with $T_{M3}=300$ minutes.

a_i	Robot 1			Robot 2			Robot 3		
	SP	MP	LP	SP	MP	LP	SP	MP	LP
a_1	6	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
a_2	0	2	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
a_3	0	4	1	0	0	0	3	2	0
a_4	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	4	2
a_5	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	4
a_6	3	0	0	0	4	3	0	0	0
a_7	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	2
a_8	0	0	0	0	4	4	3	0	0
a_9	6	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
a_{10}	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
N_{max}	33			18			44		
T_{max}	299.83			298.57			299.90		

6. Evaluation and comparison by simulation models

In this study, a simulation of the last-mile logistics operation in the historic city centre of Bari (Italy) shown in Fig. 6 is performed.

Figure 6. Customer distribution in the historic city centre of Bari (Italy)

The adopted approach differs according to the processes: for Process A the simulation is carried out using Google Maps to determine delivery times for each customer and consider the traffic conditions; for Process B the SUMO traffic simulator software is used to simulate robots travelling in the city and to check the optimization solutions in slightly realistic conditions. The SUMO program is an open source, portable, microscopic and continuous multi-modal traffic simulation package designed to handle large networks.

6.1 Simulation Results: Process A

To simulate the delivery Process A, we consider the same characteristics of the optimization: only one truck driver for each zone and $N=100$ requested deliveries per day for Zone A. The working time is 8 hours with breaks of 1 hour, which corresponds to $T = 420$ minutes.

The simulation is developed with Google Maps, using three parking areas: the courier picks up the package from the truck and walks to the customer. Figure 7 shows the sequences of operations performed to determine the total delivery time (T_A) of the truck driver for Process A.

Figure 7. Sequences of last-mile delivery activities in process A

Then, Table 12 and 13 shows respectively the delivery time (t_{Ai}) and the total delivery time ($\tau_{A,i}^s$ and $\tau_{A,i}^t$) of the truck driver obtained in each zone by the simulation of delivery Process A. It is pointed out that the parking area number 1, which serves sub-zones a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , and a_4 is located beyond the peri-urban road and therefore the truck driver has to cross this road. To cross it there is a pedestrian traffic light that requires additional time. Thus, for the same distance this parking area requires more time to serve the associated sub-zones unlike the other parking areas (2 and 3). The simulation results are reported in Table 14. The smaller number of the delivered parcels by the courier in Table 14 ($N_{max} = 70$) with respect to Table 7 ($N_{max} = 70$) is due to the presence of traffic in the simulation.

Table 12. Process A: Delivery times t_{Ai} obtained by the simulation

a_i	d_i (m)	t_{Ai} (min)
a_1	100	4.00
a_2	200	6.00
a_3	300	8.00
a_4	400	10.00
a_5	100	2.00
a_6	200	4.00
a_7	300	6.00
a_8	400	8.00
a_9	100	2.00
a_{10}	200	4.00

Table 13. Process A: Total delivery times $\tau_{A,i}^s$ and $\tau_{A,i}^t$ obtained by simulation

<i>Parking areas</i>	a_i	d_i (m)	$\tau_{A,i}^s$	$\tau_{A,i}^t$
1	a_1	100	7.00	9.00
	a_2	200	9.00	11.00
	a_3	300	11.00	13.00
	a_4	400	13.00	15.00
2	a_5	100	5.00	7.00
	a_6	200	7.00	9.00
	a_7	300	9.00	11.00
	a_8	400	11.00	13.00
3	a_9	100	5.00	7.00
	a_{10}	200	7.00	9.00

Table 14. Process A: Number of parcels delivered by the truck driver in $T=420$ minutes by the simulation

a_i	SP	MP	LP
a_1	6	4	1
a_2	4	2	0
a_3	5	1	0
a_4	6	0	0
a_5	4	3	1
a_6	4	4	0
a_7	3	0	0
a_8	4	0	0
a_9	6	3	0
a_{10}	6	3	0
Total	48	20	2
N_{max}	70		
T_{max}	417.00		

6.2 Simulation Results: Process B

The simulation of the last-mile delivery for Process B is based on the same data used for the optimization with the object of 100 parcels to be delivered. The pedestrian roads of each zone are reported from OpenStreet Maps to SUMO and the historic city centre of Bari is modelled, as shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. The historic city centre of Bari (Italy) in SUMO

In each zone, we added pedestrians and cyclists to the traffic to obtain more realistic results. The traffic flow parameters used in the SUMO simulation are: 700 pedestrians and 300 bicycles in the historic city centre; 75 cars over one hour are considered moving along the peri-urban road. These conditions are evaluated by considering the historical data of a workday of summertime in the pedestrian area, and in the peri-urban road.

The three robots are of the following types: two Avride robots (<https://www.avride.ai/robot>) with an average speed of 6 km/h in sub-zones $a_1 - a_5$ and with an average speed of 8 km/h in sub-zones $a_6 - a_{10}$; one Starship robot (<https://robotrends.ru/robopedia/starship>), with an average speed of 16 km/h in all the subzones. These two robot models ensure a working battery autonomy of more than 12 hours, as stated in the respective technical data sheet published online (Avride for 12 hours and Starship for 18 hours).

Figure 9 illustrates a screenshot of the simulation in the SUMO program, where robots (red dots) are shown making deliveries. The hub is represented by a red dot. Table 12 shows the total delivery time T_{max} obtained by the simulation. The comparison with the optimization results reveals a slight difference between the value of T_{max} calculated by the optimization for delivery the 100 parcels and the one obtained by the simulation. The presence of traffic obviously determines an increase of the delivery times. However, the results show that the optimization provides a sufficiently robust solution.

Figure 9. Screenshot obtained by SUMO

Table 15. Results comparison of total delivery time obtained by optimization and simulation for Process B

	Robot 1	Robot 2	Robot 3
T_{max} obtained by the optimization	337.1	337.9	336.7
T_{max} obtained by the simulation	342.7	343.1	342.3

6.3 Results discussion

To assess the consistency of the proposed scenarios this section provides a comparison of the results. In detail, Fig. 10 compares the number of small, medium and large parcels delivered per day performed by truck driver and robots (Process A and B).

Based on the obtained results, delivery Process B appears to be more efficient in terms of number of parcels delivered per day with respect to delivery Process A.

Figure 10. Comparison of number of parcels delivered per day in Process A and B

Figure 11 compares the numbers of parcels delivered by the robots considering their different speed.

Figure 11. Comparison of number of small, medium, and large parcels delivered per day by truck driver and robots

Analysing the data shown in the figures, the simulation results show an increase in average delivery times. This aspect is due to the simulation's incorporation of street traffic, which obviously reduces the robot's speed. Furthermore, based on the simulation findings, we can conclude that increasing the robots' speed (always to a value congruent with safety) across all routes produces a good benefit in terms of packages delivered.

Considering the total delivery time of a truck driver (Process A) per day as shown in the previous tables, it follows that Scenarios with robots (Process B) are always the best with respect to Process A. However, it is important to emphasise that the analysis focused on the delivery of the last mile in a pedestrian area, such as the historic city centre. The problem of few parking spaces along the peri-urban street and the no access vehicles area requires a delivery on foot by the truck driver. The use of an autonomous robot becomes appropriate under these conditions, but this result cannot be extended to all areas of the city.

6.4 Sensitivity analysis results

The parameters chosen for the case study are derived from the study and analysis of real cases, but the number of parcels used is not related to a real case but is a virtual value used to test the problem. Therefore, it is worth checking what happens to the results by changing the value of the parameters and analysing how these changes affect the output.

In this section, a sensitivity analysis is proposed to analyse the results. Starting with a number of parcels equal to 100 as a baseline, different scenarios are proposed by increasing these parcels in different sizes and weights. Small, Medium, Large and mix of these are considered in the analysis with an increasing percentage of 20%, 40% and 60%. The total number of parcels to be delivered, the number of parcels delivered and total delivery time for the three robots (R1, R2, R3) used for the last mile delivery are shown in Table 16.

Table 16. Results of sensitivity analysis

	Scenarios	Parcels to be delivered	Parcels delivered	R1	R2	R3
1	100 + 20% small parcels	120	120	382.1	382.35	383.5
2	100 + 40% small parcels	140	140	442.0	440.8	442.1
3	100 + 60% small parcels	160	159	478.3	468.7	476.5
4	100 + 20% medium parcels	120	120	407.4	377.9	408.5
5	100 + 40% medium parcels	140	140	461.6	462.1	459.4
6	100 + 60% medium parcels	160	154	471.4	479.3	478.0
7	100 + 20% large parcels	120	120	443.8	434.4	443.3
8	100 + 40% large parcels	140	131	470.4	477.6	477.0
9	100 + 60% large parcels	160	131	477.7	478.4	477.4
10	100 + 20% mix parcels	130	130	444.9	447.8	449.0
11	100 + 40% mix parcels	160	148	470.8	464.2	479.7
12	100 + 60% mix parcels	190	156*	476.0	472.8	476.1

The sensitive analysis considered 12 scenarios, and the results show that the number of parcels delivered with the three robots increases to a threshold value, based on the maximum time constraint. Moreover, the sizes and weights affect the number of parcels delivered: small parcels can be transported in greater numbers per trip than medium and large parcels and therefore have threshold values that are closer to the target.

Having reached the limit value even by increasing the number of packages to be delivered this obviously does not increase because the resources, i.e., the available time of the robots, have been saturated. The only exception to this principle is found in scenario 12: as the number of parcels to be delivered increases, the limit value also increases. This phenomenon depends on the increase in parcels, and in particular small parcels, which allows the optimization problem to make more multiple trips (with this type of parcel than others) and thus more deliveries. In fact, analyzing the results, 8 trips with medium parcels (2 parcels per trip) were replaced with 8 trips with small parcels (3 parcels per trip). In fact, analysing the results, in scenario 12, eight trips with medium parcels (2 parcels per trip) were replaced with eight trips with small parcels (3 parcels per trip), compared to scenario 11. This change allowed for a greater number of delivered packages without increasing the number of trips.

Overall, the sensitivity analysis shows that the results obtained can be generalized even from data not referring to a specific real case study.

6.5 *Managerial insights*

Recently, several municipal governments are adopting new policies to reduce urban congestion and increase road safety for vulnerable users. Actions such as reducing the speed of vehicles in the city, increasing pedestrian zones, bicycle lanes, and dedicated lanes for public transportation are increasingly common. Increased urban deliveries combined with the traffic policies described require more effective last-mile delivery models.

Simulations show significant efficiency benefits, especially in pedestrian and highly urbanized areas, in using autonomous robots for last-mile delivery.

Technological advances are already providing commercially attractive products. Experiments and commercial uses can be found in several Countries such as US and China. From the economic, environmental and social points of view, some studies (Silvestri et al. 2024) show how the reduction of investment cost and the number of packages delivered become the main factors in the advantage of this approach (process B) over the traditional one (process A). The economic impacts with use of delivery robots in new urban development concepts will become significant for companies that first become involved in these new logistics models.

In Europe, authorizing the use of autonomous robots on public roads is one of the biggest issues, unlike in the United States and China where they already started using them.

7. Conclusions

This paper presents an approach for enhancing last-mile delivery by comparing truck driver (Process A) and use of hub and delivery with robots (Process B). The increase in urban home deliveries, traffic congestion, and citizen demands to reduce the impacts generated by freight transport in last-mile delivery need the use of innovative logistics models. Cities are transforming, and the increase in pedestrian areas combined with reduced vehicle speeds become major constraints on the traditional delivery approach carried out by trucks.

With this aim, the main goal of the proposed study is to reduce traffic congestion by using a novel approach: trucks unload goods inside hubs and last-mile delivery is entrusted to autonomous robots that mainly use paths in pedestrian areas and sidewalks.

To address this challenge, an optimization problem with the objective of maximizing the number of parcels delivered in a given time was developed. The constraints consider robots transport capacity of parcels and the minimum number of deliveries to perform in each sub-zone. This methodology is applied in a case study developed in a pedestrian area in the city of Bari, Italy. In particular, the solution obtained by the optimization has been compared under more realistic circumstances by a simulation analysis using SUMO software. These simulations consider the impact of road traffic, which has the potential to impact the efficiency of the delivery system.

Theoretical implications of the work highlight that unlike other literature studies, the proposed approach allows analysing consistent results. These results are obtained using a methodology that involved the development of optimization and simulation. The parameter data are collected from real situations in the area under consideration, as the software used simulates scenarios based on real cartography and traffic inputs.

The analysis results highlight the advantages of Process B over process A in pedestrian areas and zones with traffic congestion problems (few parking spaces and low vehicle speeds). In simulations, considering the use of three robots, number of parcels delivered turns out to be 30% higher in less time. It would be appropriate to assess the economic, environmental, and social impacts this model generates to identify potential commercial development.

Future research will focus on evaluating the proposed strategy by including a larger number of robots operating in different urban zones, as well as the battery charging problems. Moreover, the economic analysis about the costs associated with robots, hubs and their human operators will be investigated.

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